

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Prescribers on Antibiotic Use

Geraldine Joyce Chia Chye Hsia, Evangelin Hii Hui Hui, Kiu Sie Hoong, Munirah Ahmat, Radin Mardhiah Radin Abdul Rahman

Department of Pharmacy, Sibu Hospital

NMRR-19-1123-46866

Introduction

- The increase in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a worldwide health issue, which can lead to prolonged illness, increased healthcare cost, morbidity and mortality.
- This fuels the need for new drugs but no new major class of antimicrobial has been found since late 1980s.¹
- AMR is also an issue in Sibu Hospital as internal report showed 626 cases of multidrug-resistant organisms between January to November 2018.
- Excessive use and misuse of antibiotics are considered the primary factors that accelerate the AMR process.¹
- This study aims to study the knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) of prescribers in Sibu Hospital on the rational use of antibiotics and AMR.

Material and methods

- A cross-sectional, observational study was conducted between September to November 2019 in Sibu Hospital.
- A self-administered online questionnaire adopted and modified from an earlier study² ($\alpha=0.654$) was used.
- The link to the online questionnaire (created using Google Forms) was emailed to the prescribers.

- Data were analysed using SPSS software.

Results

Table 1: Demographics

Average Age	28 years
Male	44.6%
Average Years of Experience	3 years

Response rate: 14.5%

Fig. 2: Proportion of prescribers in different levels of position

Fig. 3: Proportion of prescribers in different departments

Results

Knowledge

Fig. 4: Proportions of correct and wrong answers in the knowledge section.

- Median knowledge score was 5.
- 3.6% (both were specialists) had full score.
- >85% had good knowledge on antibiotic selection (Q1-5).
- >70% had **poor** knowledge on local resistance rate (Q7-8).
- Prescribers from surgical based departments were more aware of local resistance rate than their non-surgical colleagues ($P=0.036$).
- Specialists had better knowledge than their juniors ($P=0.024$).

Attitude

- Most of the prescribers acknowledged that AMR is a problem at the global, national and local levels.
- The levels of position did not affect their confidence on antibiotic use ($P=0.678$).
- All respondents would review antibiotic prescriptions with a senior colleague.
- Almost all respondents agreed on the importance of knowledge on antibiotics in their career and would like to have educational programmes on antibiotic use.

Practice

Fig. 5: Usefulness of different sources of information.

Fig. 6: Antibiotic teaching received during 2018.

- 44.6% of prescribers agreed that patient's demand for antibiotics contribute to overuse in their practice.
- Less than half (37.5%) of the respondents would avoid the use of restricted antibiotics due to need to apply for approval.

Discussion

- More than half of the prescribers were unable to answer the questions on dosage reduction of antibiotics and local resistance rate.
- Awareness of AMR was high among the respondents, which is also observed in studies in Peru and Kedah.^{2,3}
- Most of the respondents reported that information from senior colleagues were useful and all of them would review antibiotic prescriptions with senior colleagues.
- Antibiotic teaching should be enhanced as about 25% of the prescribers did not receive any form of antibiotic teaching at all in 2018.
- The main limitation of this study was the low response rate. There may be different understanding or interpretation of the questions as this was a self-administered questionnaire. Social desirability bias may be present.

Conclusion

- The prescribers in Sibu Hospital had moderately good knowledge on rational use of antibiotics.
- Antibiotic teaching should be enhanced. Target areas in future educational interventions may include dosage reduction of antibiotics and local resistance rate.
- Dissemination of information on local resistance rate need to be improved to enhance their knowledge on local resistance rate.
- In future, this study could be improved with a better research method, for example an interviewer-administered questionnaire.

Acknowledgement

- We would like to thank Director General of Health for the permission to present this poster, Mdm Chuo Sing Hong for her support and guidance, and all the prescribers who participated in the study.

References

- Holloway K, van Dijk L. The World Medicines Situation 2011: Rational Use of Medicines. 3rd ed. Geneva: WHO Press, World Health Organization; 2011.
- Garcí C, Llamocca L, Garcí K, Jiménez A, Samalvides F, Gotuzzo E et al. Knowledge, attitudes and practice survey about antimicrobial resistance and prescribing among physicians in a hospital setting in Lima, Peru. BMC Clinical Pharmacology. 2011;11(1).
- Tan WL, Shahfina I, Zuraidah A. Knowledge, attitude and practice of antibiotics prescribing among medical officers of public health care facilities in the state of Kedah, Malaysia. Med J Malaysia. 2015; 70(5)